

Studies on 4-Hydroxy Coumarins

N. C. Misra, K. K. Patnaik and M. K. Rout

A number of 3-substituted amino methyl 4-hydroxy coumarins have been synthesised by application of the Mannich reaction. Thiazolyl amines were used as the amine components because of their active pharmacological properties. Some of the compounds have been tested for their antispasmodic and antihistaminic properties.

The present investigation describes the preparation of some 3-substituted amino methyl 4-hydroxy coumarins by the application of Mannich reaction. The 4-hydroxy coumarins were prepared by the reaction of the appropriate phenol and malonic acid in the presence of anhydrous zinc chloride and phosphorus oxychloride by the method of Shah *et al.*¹

The 4-hydroxy coumarins (2,4-chromandiones) prepared by the above method were (i) 4-hydroxy coumarin, (ii) 4,7-dihydroxy coumarin, (iii) 4-hydroxy-7-methyl coumarin, (iv) 4-hydroxy-6,7-benzocoumarin, and (v) 4-hydroxy-7,8-benzocoumarin.

The Mannich bases were prepared by the method of Robertson and Link² by pouring a solution of the amine (1.25 mole) and formaldehyde (1 mole) in absolute ethanol into a solution of the appropriate 4-hydroxy coumarin (1 mole) in absolute ethanol. Another method i.e., mixing the amine and the 4-hydroxy coumarin prior to the addition of formaldehyde also gave satisfactory results.

The primary and secondary amines used were (i) 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole, (iii) 2-amino-4-*p*-tolyl thiazole, (iii) 2-amino-6-methyl benzothiazole, (iv) 2-amino-6-nitro benzothiazole, (v) 2-amino-6-chloro benzothiazole and (vi) piperidine. They were prepared by the standard methods described in the literature.

In some cases, the reaction proceeded very rapidly, the products separating out immediately.

The substituted amino methyl group was assumed to be attached to position-3 in view of the already known reactivity of the 3-position of the 4-hydroxy coumarin in the aldol, Michael addition reaction and similar compounds prepared by Robertson and Link².

EXPERIMENTAL

3-(4'-phenyl-2'-thiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy coumarin: To a solution of 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole (2.6 g) dissolved in absolute ethanol (25 ml.), formalin (0.5 ml.) was added. This was followed by adding a solution of 4-hydroxy coumarin (2.02 g.) in absolute ethanol (50 ml.) at room temperature. The mixture was placed in the refrigerator. The product

1. Shah *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, 25, 677.

2. Robertson and Link, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1883.

that separated was filtered and washed with ether. By diluting the mother liquor, additional quantities of the compound separated out.

Other compounds of the series were prepared by following the above procedure. In case of the derivatives of piperidine, however, the alcoholic solutions of piperidine with formalin and the coumarin were heated to the boiling point, then mixed and allowed to cool.

The analytical data of the derivatives are given in Table I.

TABLE I

(a) *Mannich bases from 4-hydroxy coumarin :*

Sl. no.	2-amino thiazole derivative	Product	Yield %	M.P. °C	% of S	
					Found	Calc.
1.	4-Phenyl	3-(4'-phenyl-2'-thiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy coumarin	60	208	9.02	9.14
2.	4- <i>p</i> -tolyl	3-(4'- <i>p</i> -tolyl-2'-thiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy coumarin.	50	175	8.68	8.79
<i>2-amino benzothiazole derivatives</i>						
3.	6-methyl	3-(6'-methyl-2'-benzothiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy coumarin	55	240	9.18	9.46
4.	6 Chloro	3-(6'-chloro-2'-benzothiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy coumarin	50	221	8.71	8.92
5.	6-Nitro	3-(6'-nitro-2'-benzothiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy coumarin	45	234	8.58	8.67

(b) *Mannich bases from 4,7-dihydroxy coumarin*

2-amino thiazole derivatives

6.	4-Phenyl	3-(4'-phenyl-2'-thiazolyl) aminomethyl-4,7-dihydroxy coumarin	75	240	8.62	8.74
7.	4- <i>p</i> -Tolyl	3-(4'- <i>p</i> -tolyl-2'-thiazolyl) aminomethyl-4,7-dihydroxy coumarin	70	238	8.11	8.42
8.	6-methyl	3-(6'-methyl-2'-benzothiazolyl) aminomethyl-4,7-dihydroxy coumarin	65	232	8.82	9.03
9.	6-Chloro	3-(6'-chloro-2'-benzothiazolyl) aminomethyl-4,7-dihydroxy coumarin	55	204	8.31	8.54
10.	6-Nitro	3-(6'-nitro-2'-benzothiazolyl) aminomethyl-4,7-dihydroxy coumarin	55	240	8.08	8.31

(c) Mannich bases from 4-hydroxy 7-methyl coumarin :

Sl. no.	2-amino thiazole derivative	Product	Yield %	M.P. °C	% of S	
					Found	Calc.
<i>2-amino thiazole derivatives</i>						
11.	4-Phenyl	3-(4'-phenyl-2'-thiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy 7-methyl coumarin	65	234	8.62	8.79
12.	4-p-tolyl	3-(4'-p-tolyl-2'-thiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-7-methyl coumarin	65	235	8.15	8.46
<i>2-aminobenzothiazole derivatives</i>						
13.	6-Chloro	3-(6'-chloro-2'-benzothiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-7-methyl coumarin	60	249	8.36	8.59
14.	6-Methyl	3-(6'-methyl-2'-benzothiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-7-methyl coumarin	60	226	8.87	9.09
15.	6-Nitro	3-(6'-nitro-2'-benzothiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-7-methyl coumarin	60	195	8.31	8.35

(d) Mannich bases from 4-hydroxy-7,8-benzo coumarin :

<i>2-amino thiazole derivatives</i>						
16.	4-Phenyl	3-(4'-phenyl-2'-thiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-7,8-benzo coumarin	65	239	7.88	8.00
17.	4-p-tolyl	3-(4'-p-tolyl-2'-thiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-7,8-benzo coumarin	70	250	7.68	7.73
18.	6-Methyl	3-(6'-methyl-2'-benzo thiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-7,8-benzo coumarin	70	221	8.15	8.24
19.	6-Nitro	3-(6'-nitro-2'-benzothiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-7,8-benzo coumarin	65	200	7.49	7.63
20.	6-Chloro	3-(6'-chloro-2'-benzothiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-7,8-benzo coumarin	70	234	7.78	7.83

(e) Mannich bases from 4-hydroxy-6,7-benzo coumarin :

<i>2-amino thiazole derivatives</i>						
21.	4-Phenyl	3-(4'-phenyl-2'-thiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-6,7-benzo coumarin	70	220	7.82	8.00
22.	4-p-Tolyl	3-(4'-p-tolyl-2'-thiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-6,7-benzo coumarin	65	235	7.68	7.73
<i>2-amino benzothiazole derivatives</i>						
23.	6-Methyl	3-(6'-methyl-2'-benzothiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-6,7-benzo coumarin	65	240	7.09	8.24
24.	6-Chloro	3-(6'-chloro-2'-benzothiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-6,7-benzo coumarin	70	210	7.47	7.83
25.	6-Nitro	3-(6'-nitro-2'-benzothiazolyl) aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-6,7-benzo coumarin	65	260	7.49	7.63

TABLE II

Mannich bases from substituted 4-hydroxy coumarins and piperidine

Sl. no.	Coumarin	Product	Yield %	M.P. °C	% of N	
					Found	Calc.
1.	4-Hydroxy	3-Piperidino methyl-4-hydroxy coumarin	75	182	5.30	5.40
2.	4,7-dihydroxy	3-Piperidino methyl-4,7-dihydroxy coumarin	75	260*	4.92	5.09
3.	4-Hydroxy-6,7-benzo coumarin	3-Piperidino methyl-4-hydroxy-6,7-benzo coumarin	70	245	4.48	4.53
4.	4-hydroxy-7,8-benzo coumarin	3-Piperidino methyl-4-hydroxy-7,8-benzo coumarin	65	230	4.49	4.53

* Denotes decomposition.

Antispasmodic and antihistaminic tests : The tests were carried on strips of Guinea Pig ileum in a Dale's isolated organ bath using acetyl choline hydrochloride in a concentration of 5 μ gm./50 ml (for antispasmodic tests) and histamine acid phosphate in a similar concentration (for antihistaminic tests) as spasmogens for inducing contractions. Among the compounds tested it was found that the compound nos. 3, 16, and 24 blocked the effect of standard doses of acetyl choline to the extent of 50% at a concentration of less than 2 mg. per 50 ml. Similarly compound nos. 1, 16, 18 and 20 inhibited 50% of spasm induced by standard doses of histamine at concentrations of less than 2 mg. per 50 ml.

We are thankful to the Board of Scientific and Industrial Research, Orissa, for research grants to carry out the investigation.

Department of Chemistry,
Revenshaw College,
Cuttack-3.

Received April 29, 1970